

COMPOUNDS OF MANGANOUS CHLORIDE WITH HETEROCYCLIC BASES AND SECONDARY AND TERTIARY AMINES

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The complex compounds of manganese have been prepared by the action of manganous chloride on some heterocyclic bases and secondary and tertiary amines in alcoholic medium.

Reitzenstein (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1898, 18, 253) prepared dipyridino-manganous chloride, $MnCl_2.(C_5H_5N)_2$, and diquinolino-manganous chloride, $MnCl_2.(C_8H_7N)_2$, by adding an excess of pyridine or quinoline respectively to a solution of manganous chloride in alcohol. Hayes (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 24, 360) obtained the compound, $C_5H_5N.MnCl_2.HCl$, by adding a solution of $MnCl_2$ in HCl to a solution of pyridine hydrochloride. Dubsky and Dostal (Pub. faculte Sci. Univ. Masaryk, No. 196, 17-23, 1934) studied the formation of quinoline (Q) complexes: (i) $MnCl_2(Q)_2.3H_2O$, and (ii) $(MnCl_2)_2H_2(Q)_2.2H_2O$. Sacconi (*Ann. Chim. Rome*, 40, 386, 150) obtained with nicotinamide (NA), the complex compound, $MnCl_2.2(NA)$. It is evident that very little work has been done on the formation of compounds of manganous chloride with heterocyclic bases, and no work has been done on the formation of compounds with secondary and tertiary amines. The present investigation was therefore undertaken with a view to studying the preparation and properties of these compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

The heterocyclic bases and amines used were of B.D.H. 'Pure' quality and alcohol was dehydrated and redistilled. Manganous chloride was dehydrated by passing HCl gas over hydrated manganous chloride at 160°.

Manganous chloride and the organic substances were dissolved separately in alcohol and the compounds were prepared by two methods. In the first case, the organic substance was added to the manganous chloride solution slowly, with constant stirring, till it was in slight excess. In the second case, the manganous chloride solution was added to the organic compound till it was in slight excess. If a precipitate was not obtained in either of the cases, the solution was evaporated slowly on a sand-bath, when the compound separated out. It was kept for about an hour, filtered, washed with alcohol, dried at low temperatures and analysed.

Manganese was estimated as $Mn_2P_2O_7$ and chlorine as AgCl. Alcohol of crystallisation was estimated by heating the substance to a constant weight at 100° and noting down the loss in weight. The organic substance was found by difference.

TABLE I

Manganous chloride-heterocyclic bases.

Base.	Compound formed.	Colour.	% Manganese.		% Chlorine.		% Org. matter.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Piperidine	Mono-piperidino-M * MnCl ₂ .C ₅ H ₁₁ N.	Dark brown	27.25	26.05	33.46	33.64	39.29	40.37
Quinoline	Mono-quinolino-M MnCl ₂ .C ₈ H ₇ N.	Light brown	20.59	21.55	26.75	27.83	52.66	50.62
γ -Picoline	Mono-alcoholo- mono- γ -picolino-M MnCl ₂ .C ₆ H ₇ N.C ₂ H ₅ OH	Light rosy	20.48	20.73	26.62	26.77	35.80	35.73
Piperazine	Mono-piperazino-di-M 2MnCl ₂ .(C ₄ H ₁₀ N ₂)	Dark brown	33.54	32.53	42.38	42.01	24.08	25.46
Nicotine	Mono-nicotino-di-M 2MnCl ₂ .(C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂)	White	26.13	26.16	34.75	34.29	59.12	59.15

* M = Manganous chloride.

TABLE II

Manganous chloride-secondary and tertiary amines.

Amines.	Compound formed.	Colour	% Manganese.		% Chlorine.		% Org. matter.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Dimethyl- aniline	Mono-dimethylanilino-M MnCl ₂ .C ₆ H ₅ N(CH ₃) ₂	Dark blue	23.79	22.25	28.39	28.73	48.42	49.02
Diethyl- aniline	Mono-diethylanilino-M MnCl ₂ .C ₆ H ₅ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	Grey	19.81	19.97	26.34	25.79	53.85	54.24
Dimethyl- <i>o</i> - toluidine	Mono-dimethyl- <i>o</i> - toluidino-M MnCl ₂ .CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₃) ₂	Do	20.52	21.05	27.61	27.18	51.87	51.77
Dimethyl- <i>p</i> - toluidine	Mono-dimethyl- <i>p</i> -toluidino-M MnCl ₂ .CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₃) ₂	Brick-red	20.49	21.05	28.43	27.18	51.08	51.77
Triethyl- amine	Mono-triethylamino-M MnCl ₂ .(C ₂ H ₅) ₃ N	White	23.64	24.19	32.17	31.24	44.79	44.57
Dibenzyl- amine	Mono-dibenzylamino-M MnCl ₂ .(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂) ₂ NH	Brown	16.39	17.01	22.69	21.97	60.92	61.02
Tribenzyl- amine	Mono-tribenzylamino-M MnCl ₂ .(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂) ₃ N	White	14.07	13.30	18.06	17.18	67.87	69.52

M = Manganous chloride.

DISCUSSION

Manganese being a transitional element, should exhibit a tendency to form complex compounds readily, but the same is lowered considerably when it is in divalent state. The tendency is further depressed in the case of secondary and tertiary amines due

to weak co-ordinating power of the nitrogen atom with the result that unstable compounds, in which the ratio of $MnCl_2$: amine = 1:1 are formed. The instability of the compounds is probably due to the fact that neither the E. A. N. assumes the inert gas configuration nor there is any symmetry in the structure:

All the compounds with heterocyclic bases are stable except that obtained with nicotine, which is unstable and turns black and is rendered viscous on exposure to atmosphere. The compound with piperazine, which is fairly stable, can be represented as:

All the compounds hydrolyse readily on boiling with water and are decomposed by mineral acids. These do not give a sharp melting point and probably decompose when heated at a high temperature. When heated with sodalime, the liquid base separates out.

Thanks are due to Dr. S. S. Joshi, D.Sc., Head of the Chemistry Department, for providing necessary facilities.

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Received June 13, 1958.